

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON TREATMENT OF TEXTILE DYE WASTE - WATERS IN THE BIOREACTOR AND CONSTRUCTED WETLAND

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ABSTRACT

We report biological treatment of textile dye wastewater of Sangner industry at different retention time (RT) in the bioreactor and constructed wetland separately and also in combination. Their performance was assessed in terms of improvement of physico-chemical characteristics of the treated wastewaters and toxicity reduction estimated using duckweed and fish bioassays. The efficacy of bioreactor and wetland improved with increase in RT and bioreactor was found more effective in reducing COD, BOD and color removal of wastewaters while wetland in reducing toxicity to duckweed and fish. Bioreactor and wetland in combination were found more effective in treating textile wastewaters reducing values of COD and BOD within permissible limits of discharge in the water bodies. However, toxicity of treated wastewater was still higher and did not decrease even after polishing with alum.

INTRODUCTION

Textile industry uses large quantity of freshwater at various steps of printing, and therefore, volume of wastewater produced is equally large. Most of the wastewater is discharged either untreated or after partial treatment. Its disposal in the water bodies deteriorates water qualities affecting flora and fauna adversely (Sharma et al. 2003), whereas land disposal may contaminate groundwater (Kesvan and Parmeswari 2005, Balakrishnan et al. 2008, Geetha et al. 2008). The application of textile dye wastewater in agriculture had led to biomagnification of heavy metals in the crops, vegetables and even in milk (Sharma et al. 1999, 2001) and also of dyes in vegetables (Zhou 2001).

The Water (pollution & control) Act (1974) has made it mandatory to treat textile dye wastewater within permissible limit prior to disposal on the land/in the water bodies. Small scale industries contributing maximum to textile printing in the country are however, reluctant to install effluent treatment plant because of its higher installation as well as operational cost. With this background, two bench scale studies were made in the greenhouse to optimize cost effective biological treatment of textile wastewater and important findings are reported in this communication.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The efficacy of bioreactor and constructed wetland was assessed separately and also in combination to treat textile dye wastewater of Sangner. The treated wastewater was

finally passed through sand filter. Salient features of bioreactor, constructed wetland and sand filter used are detailed below.

Bioreactor

The bioreactor developed in 13L sized plastic bucket (Length= 29cm; Width= 27cm) had an outlet about 2" below the bucket top (Fig. 1). About 2" thick layer of stone grit (Length = 2.0- 3.0cm; Width = 1.0- 1.5 cm) was laid on the bucket floor. Four earthen pots (volume = 300ml) were placed inverted over the grit layer in such a manner, as to hold one long plastic pipe (Length = 35.0cm; Diameter = 2.0cm) in the centre. The second pipe (Length = 20.0 cm; Diameter = 1.6cm) was however, kept close to the outlet. A rubber tube (Length = 50.0 cm; Diameter = 0.7cm) was inserted in the second pipe in such a manner that its one end was close to the open end of earthen pots resting on grit layer at the bucket floor (Fig. 1). The other end of the tube lying outside the pipe was closed by a stopper. The available space in the bucket was filled with grit collected from a bioreactor developed by an earlier worker in the laboratory (Kumar et al. 2006). The development of microbial biofilm over the grit was initiated by charging the bioreactor (through its central pipe), with a mixture of outflows from bioreactor and wetland of ETP in Sangner for 7 days. Thereafter, textile wastewater collected from the equalization tank of ETP was regularly fed for a period of 15 days. The removal of stopper drained wastewater gradually from the bioreactor almost completely

and allowed influx of atmospheric air in the void space between the grits favoring aerobic microbial degradation. After two hours of effluent discharge, bioreactor was reloaded with untreated textile wastewater displacing air filled in the void space thereby resulting in anoxic condition. Microbial community of the bioreactor therefore, experienced both oxic and anoxic conditions.

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram of Bioreactor of Bench Scale Study

Constructed wetland

Constructed wetlands raised in 15L sized plastic buckets (Length = 35.0 cm; Diameter = 33.0cm) by the earlier worker in the laboratory were used in the present study (Bhardwaj, 2002). Their hydraulic format was vertical upflow (Fig. 2) and solid matrix was a mixture of grit (Large sized: Length = 2.5 cm; Width = 1.5cm and Small sized: Length = 1.5 cm; Width = 0.8cm) and coarse river sand (ratio = 1:3). More than 2 years old shoots of *Phragmites karka* were planted in the solid matrix.

Sand Filter

13L sized plastic bucket (Length = 29.0 cm; Diameter = 27.0 cm) with an outlet 2" above the bucket floor was used to develop the sand filter having solid matrix made of following components:

- i. Mixture of grit (Large sized: Length= 2.5 cm; Width = 1.5cm and Small sized: (Length= 1.5 cm; Width = 0.8cm)

- ii. Coarse sand (River bed)

About 3" thick slant of grit was made over the bucket floor at the outlet, in such a manner that large sized grit layer (2" thick) was overlapped by the small one. Finally 3/4th of the bucket was filled with coarse river sand (Fig.3).

Fig. 2. Schematic Diagram of Constructed Wetland

Fig. 3. Schematic Diagram of Sand Filter

Loading pattern of wastewater

A known volume of wastewater added gradually to the bioreactor through the central pipe using a funnel was however, fed drop wise at a constant rate in the wetland using drip set made for intravenous influx of glucose to the patients.

Physico-chemical characteristics of untreated (inflow) and treated (effluent) wastewaters were assessed following standard methods (APHA 1989). The bioreactor and wetland outflows were measured. COD and BOD loads in both inflow and outflows, and their percentage reduction in outflows were calculated as follow.

BOD/COD load = BOD/COD (ppm) of sample x volume of inflow/outflow

Load reduction (%) = $\frac{\text{COD/BOD load in Outflows}}{\text{COD/BOD load in Inflow}} \times 100$

Spectroscopic Analysis of Textile Wastewaters

Absorption spectra (UV-visible range) of inflows and outflows (bioreactors and wetlands) were scanned by a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Model: "Cintra 20", GBC). The absorbance values of (OD value) different peaks in the visible region were used to calculate dye decolorization (%) as follow.

% reduction decolorization = $\frac{100 - \text{Absorbance of outflow spectrum}}{\text{Absorbance of inflow spectrum}} \times 100$

Toxicity assessment of wastewaters

Duckweed and fish bioassays were made to measure toxicity of untreated and treated textile dye wastewater.

Duckweed Assay

Duckweeds are ideal for toxicity testing because the test end point (plant growth) is ecologically significant. During the present study, *Lemna aquinoctialis* has been used as a test organism, since it is a locally available species growing round the year in the unpolluted concrete tanks (size = 40

× 40 × 60 cm) of University Botanical Garden for over 20 years, and hence were not exposed to pollutants. Prior to entry in to experimental protocol, plants were washed with distilled water were transferred into diluted (20%) Hoagland solution and cultured in a growth chamber for 10 days at 20 ± 2 °C and light intensity of 2100 ± 35 lux for 8hrs and 1000 ± 22 lux for remaining 16hrs. Studies were initiated by adding 20 healthy fronds (10 colonies) in a test solution for quantifying changes in frond number with time (on 4th, 7th and 10th day) while their 20 colonies for quantifying chlorophyll content as described elsewhere (Sharma 1985).

Fish Bioassay

Gambusia affinis Baird & Gerard commonly known as mosquito fish were collected from a tank in the Department of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, were acclimatized to laboratory conditions for 15 days. Thereafter, healthy fish of uniform size were starved in the tap water for 24h prior to experiment. Five to seven dilutions of wastewaters (made with tap water) were used, each having three replicates and fish were carefully transferred to the buckets (Size: 5L). An aquarium pump was used for aerating the medium during experimental period.

Physico-chemical characteristics of wastewaters were estimated at the beginning of the experiment. A daily record of mortality and behavior was maintained. The opercular movements were observed at 25 and 50% dilution of outflows. Autopsy of the surviving fish was done at the end of study (96h) for RBC counts detailed elsewhere (Sharma et al. 2003). LC/EC₅₀ values were calculated using the COMPAQ personal computer BASIC version 1.13.

Table 1. Physico-chemical characteristics of inflow and outflows from bioreactor and bioreactor + wetland

Wastewater	pH	EC (ms)	COD (mg / L) % load redn.		BOD (mg / L) % load redn	
Inflow	6.8	5.6	750.6 ± 78.4	3002.4	87.3 ± 3.1	349.2
Bioreactor outflows						
1 day RT	8.7	6.3	288.5	1154 (-62)	49.7 ± 0.6	198.8 (-43)
2 day RT	8.7	5.8	178.4	713.6 (-76)	52.7 ± 1.2	210.8 (-40)
3 day RT	8.7	5.5	148.4	593.6 (-80)	27.7 ± 1.5	110.8 (-68)
Bioreactor (1 day RT) + wetland (1 day RT) outflows						
2 day RT	9.0 ± 0.2	5.4 ± 0.6	189.2 ± 20.8	756.8 (-75)	48.7 ± 3.1	194.8 (-44)
Alum reated	8.8 ± 0.3	6.0 ± 0.9	142.1 ± 36.1	568.4 (-81)	39.0 ± 4.0	156 (-55)

Table 2. Physico-chemical characteristics of inflow and outflows from wetland, bioreactor and bioreactor + wetland

Wastewater	pH	EC (ms)	COD		BOD	
			(mg / L)	(mg / L)	(mg / L)	(mg / L)
			% load redn.		% load redn	
Inflow	8.3	5.8	369.7 ± 20.0	1109.1	40.0 ± 5.7	-
Wetland outflows						
1 day RT	8.6 ± 0.1	6.0 ± 0.6	222.2 ± 7.9	486.6 (-56)	32.6 ± 1.5	71.4 (-41)
2 day RT	8.8 ± 0.1	4.9 ± 0.1	186.6 ± 3.6	377.03 (-66)	26.8 ± 1.5	54.2 (-55)
3 day RT	8.6 ± 0.1	4.3 ± 1.2	138.6 ± 73.4	331.25 (-70)	35.0 ± 3.9	83.7 (-30)
Bioreactor outflows						
1 day RT	8.6 ± 0.3	5.3 ± 0.8	91.7 ± 6.6	366.8 (-67)	14.0 ± 1.4	56 (-53)
Bioreactor (1 day RT) + wetland (1 day RT) outflows						
2 day RT	8.9 ± 0.2	5.8 ± 0.1	137.0 ± 34.1	362.37 (-67)	8.5 ± 5.8	22.5 (-81)

Table 3. Percentage reduction in absorbance values in the visible region of spectra (400-750nm) of outflows

	Retention period	Percentage reduction in absorbance
Bioreactor outflows	1 day RT	75-82
	2 day RT	82-90
	3 day RT	90-93
Wetland outflows	1 day RT	43-58
	2 day RT	46-69
	3 day RT	46-69
Bioreactor + wetland outflows	2 day RT:	25-62
	Untreated outflow	
	Alum treated	50-77

green to white (due to chlorosis) with brown margins due to dye deposition. The magnitude of adverse effects increased with exposure period.

EC₅₀ values of bioreactor and wetland outflows increased with an increase in RT possibly on account of better degradation of toxic compound/s in the wastewater (Table 4, 5). A comparison of EC₅₀ values revealed that toxicity of bioreactor outflows were almost similar to wetland outflows at 1 and 2 days RT, but its values increased markedly for wetland outflows of 3 days RT suggesting better reduction in toxicity of the wastewater.

The treatment of wastewater simultaneously in the bioreactor and wetland (2 days RT) decreased toxicity of treated wastewater markedly in comparison to bioreactor outflows

Table 4. EC₅₀ values of inflow and outflows from bioreactor and bioreactor + wetland

Wastewater	4 th	Frono no. 7 th	10 th	Chlorophyll
Inflow	126.9**	64.2**	42.3**	6.1**
Bioreactor outflows				
1 day RT	82.3**	68.7**	58.9	67.8
2 day RT	99.1**	84.5	79.2*	75.8**
3 day RT	126.2	76.0**	67.5*	71.7**
Bioreactor (1 day RT) + wetland outflow (1 day RT) + Alum treatment				
2 day RT	464.2	726.3	145.321	111.8**

** 1%, * 5%

Table 5. EC₅₀ values of inflow and wetland outflows

Wastewater	Frond no.			Chlorophyll
	7 th	4 th	10 th	
Inflow	34.4	30.8	29.8	28.1*
Wetland outflows				
1 day RT	55.3	52.3	51.8	58.4
2 day RT	88.1	80.9	78.2	64.1**
3 day RT	111.5	146.7	151.9	80.1**

** 1%, * 5%

Table 6. LC₅₀ values of inflow and outflows from bioreactor and bioreactor + wetland

Sample	Inflow	Bioreactor outflow			Bioreactor + wetland outflows	
		1day RT	2day RT	3day RT	Untreated	Alum Treated
LC ₅₀ (%)	34.38	9.4	34.4	34.4	37.5	30.6

Table 7. LC₅₀ values of inflow and outflows from wetland and bioreactor + wetland

sample	inflow	Wetland outflow			Bioreactor + wetland outflows (Untreated)
		1day RT	2day RT	3day RT	
LC ₅₀ (%)	8.0	10.0	29.17	52.08	48.33

(Table 4). Our findings suggest that wetland is more efficient in toxicity reduction of textile wastewaters.

Another interesting finding was reduction in EC₅₀ values of bioreactor outflows with exposure period whereas those for wetland outflows differed little (Table 4, 5). Thus toxicity of wetland outflows were stable whereas of bioreactor outflows increased with time possibly due to formation of new toxic compound/s.

FISH BIOASSAY

Fish moving randomly in groups were bottom dwellers in the control and at lower concentrations (<50%) of outflows from bioreactor, wetland and bioreactor + wetland but those exposed to higher concentrations of outflows (50- 100%) showed fast, irritating and jerky movements. Fish were dead in bioreactor and wetland outflows of lower concentration (25%) at 1 day RT but only in 50% concentration at 2 and 3 days RT. Opercular movements decreased (21-41%) in 25% bioreactor and wetland outflows after 24h exposure. The percentage reduction was however, lower (11-20%) after 96 h exposure in the bioreactor outflow. It however, increased in wetland outflows (38-40%). Interestingly, fish survived at these dilutions in bioreactor + wetland outflows though their operculum movement decreased (12-69%) at 24 and 96h of exposure.

Fish Mortality

1st Bench Scale Study

LC₅₀ value of bioreactor outflows was lower (9%) than inflow (LC₅₀ = 34%) at 1 day RT but it increased becoming similar to inflow (34%) at higher retention period (Table 6). Thus, bioreactor outflow toxicity increasing at 1 day RT decreased afterwards possibly on account of degradation of toxic compounds. The treatment of inflow in both bioreactor and wetland did not reduce outflow toxicity (LC₅₀ = 37%). The

polishing of bioreactor+ wetland outflows with alum was also not found effective in toxicity reduction (LC₅₀ = 30%).

2nd Bench Scale Study

LC₅₀ value of inflow (8%) was found almost similar to wetland outflow (10%) of 1 day RT. It however, increased markedly with an increase in retention period in the wetland becoming maximum at 3 day RT (52%, Table 7). However, combined treatment of wastewater (inflow) in bioreactor and wetland (2day RT) was little better than wetland alone at similar RT (Table 2). A comparison of LC₅₀ values of bioreactor outflows (9-34%) with wetland outflows (10-52%) at similar RT revealed a little higher reduction in toxicity in the constructed wetland

A comparison of LC₅₀ values of fish bioassay with EC₅₀ values for *Lemna* revealed latter to be higher (Inflow: 4 folds; Bioreactor outflows: 3-9 folds, Wetland outflows: 2-5 folds, Bioreactor + wetland outflow: 15 fold) suggesting fish to be more sensitive organism.

DISCUSSION

Azo dyes degrade under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Under anaerobic condition, many bacteria gratuitously reduce azo dyes in to colorless amines (Haug et al. 1991), Kudlich et al. 1996). They similarly degrade dyes

under aerobic condition. *Acetobacter liquefaciens* S-1 isolated from dye contaminated sludge decolorized and degraded methyl red under aerobic condition (Kudlich et al. 1997). Wong and Yuen (1996) isolated *Klebsiella pneumonia* RS 13, which decolorized and degraded methyl red aerobically, faster than *A. liquefaciens*. Moutaouakkil et al. (2004) also reported 100% decolonization of methyl red even within 6 h of incubation by *Enterobacter agglomerans*. Aerobic degradation of azo dyes is documented infrequently and typically restricted to microorganisms, which co-metabolically degrades the dyes. Both aerobic and anoxic conditions existed in the solid matrix of bioreactor and wetland rhizosphere. The loading of inflow (untreated wastewater) displaced air in the void spaces of solid matrix bioreactor and also from wetland rhizosphere. The release of wastewater from the bioreactor and evapotranspiration losses from constructed wetland facilitated influx of atmospheric air into void spaces of bioreactor and wetland rhizosphere. The microbial consortium of the bioreactor and wetland degraded dyes in the wastewaters under both in aerobic and anaerobic conditions, being faster in the former. Haug et al (1991) also made similar observations during the degradation of mordant yellow-3 by a consortium of bacteria. Dye pastes used for printing in Sanganer contain guar gum (made of polysaccharides) as thickener which might have served as soft carbon source essential for microorganisms degrading dyes co-metabolically. The bacterial and fungal species degrading dyes *in vitro* cultures and also in the bioreactor have been reported (Grover et al. 2004, Kumar et al. 2006). Although reduction in values of BOD and COD in outflows of bioreactor, wetland and bioreactor + wetland were within discharge limits imposed by Ministry of Environment & Forest, New Delhi but these were still toxic to aquatic flora and fauna, as evident from findings of duckweed and fish bioassays. The polishing of outflows with alum did not reduce outflow toxicity. Rather, it was higher. However, it may decrease after polishing of outflow by activated charcoal. Our study suggests that bioreactor in combination with wetland are more effective in treating textile wastewater since bioreactor is more efficient in improving physico-chemical characteristics of the wastewaters while wetland in reducing toxicity.

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